

Inside Bridges: Autonomous Crack Inspection with Nano UAVs in GNSS-Denied Environments

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Abstract—Detecting damage to bridges is essential for safety and financial reasons. We focus on inspections *inside* bridges and claim Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are ideally suited to assist inspections of hard-to-reach areas. Using UAVs in narrow indoor environments imposes constraints on the size of the UAV. While small UAVs are attractive for their agility and reduced risks associated with them, the need to carry cameras and sensors results in a lower bound on thrust and thus UAV and rotor size. Moreover, position and orientation control is particularly demanding inside bridges because satellite navigation is not available. To address these challenges, we implement a nano UAV that is capable of analyzing camera data for cracks with a machine learning model. UAV position is tracked with inertial measurement units, an optical flow, and a laser-based range sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

The road and train network is an essential part of the logistics of our economy, but the ever increasing traffic demands and the aging of our infrastructure risks breaking the links. Bridges are an integral part of this network. Their inspection is a laborious and often dangerous process, as damages may first become evident in hard-to-reach areas.

UAVs offer the necessary characteristics to support the inspection of bridges. The degrees of freedom provided by their design make it possible to work independently of height and thus to easily examine hard-to-reach areas. This process is guided by cameras and sensors, which can be individually mounted onto the UAV. While bridge inspection assisted by an UAV has been done several times before [1], [2], research mainly focuses on assessing bridges from the outside, where the UAV is not limited in size and power and can therefore carry heavy and high-resolution equipment. When bridges are inspected for damage from the inside, the environmental parameters change significantly, making available solutions no longer feasible.

This paper was funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe Grant Agreement number 101079342 (Fostering Opportunities Towards Slovak Excellence in Advanced Control for Smart Industries), and by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) under grant INST 213/1028-1 FUGB.

This research as part of the project “BIMKIT – Bestandsmodellierung von Gebäuden und Infrastrukturbauwerken Mittels KI zur Generierung von Digital Twins” is funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) under grant number 01MK21001J and is supported by the German Aerospace Center (DLR), Cologne.

We propose a nano UAV setup that meets the requirements for inspections inside the different parts of bridges. Our setup achieves a high level of autonomy in that it analyzes data gathered by a UAV-mounted camera for cracks during a flight in real-time. For this purpose, we combine the UAV setup with a machine-learning (ML) model specially trained for detecting cracks in bridges. Based on the position estimation of the UAV, we can locate the detected cracks with respect to the starting point of the UAV, providing an overview of crack size and crack distribution.

To validate our setup, we conduct actual flight experiments in an indoor environment along several trajectories with strategically positioned cracks. We compare the estimated position of the cracks to position measurements made with a high-precision motion capture system to determine the accuracy of the setup.

Fig. 1. Inside a concrete deck arch bridge with hollow spandrel.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We begin by examining the conditions the UAV is subject to during inspections inside bridges. Two aspects are crucial, the size of the UAV, and the availability of position information. The latter is required to achieve flights that are safe and sufficiently precise for the measurement task at hand. The analysis of these aspects leads to the choice of equipment and experimental conditions described in Sec. III. In addition, the analysis clarifies why existing experimental setups are unsuitable for the type of inspection of interest here.

Fig. 2. Crazyflie 2.1 quadcopter with attachments for autonomous indoor bridge inspection.

A. Requirements and restrictions on UAV size

For structures inside bridges, dimensions of unobstructed airspaces vary widely, from equivalent diameters of less than 30cm to more than 10m [3]. A typical example with dimensions in the range of a few meters is shown in Fig. 1. Even inside large supporting structures, voids are often partially obstructed with supporting beams that limit the overall dimensions of the available airspace [4], rendering large UAVs impractical. In addition to size restrictions that result from limited space, the ground effect, or more generally the distortion of the airflow in proximity to any surface, must be taken into account. The ground effect, which leads to unstable flight behavior [5], increases with the rotor diameter, implying that small UAVs are less subject to this effect [6].

However, reducing the rotor diameter also results in reduced thrust and thus results in a reduction of the maximum take-off weight (see e.g. [7]). In our application, the UAV needs to carry a camera, which, together with the battery required for its operation, is the heaviest equipment. Consequently, a tradeoff exists between choosing the UAV as small as possible to achieve a high versatility in narrow and obstructed airspaces, and a sufficient thrust required to carry a camera and the battery power for its operation. Note that the same tradeoff also applies to the camera itself, where a compromise of mass and power requirements versus resolution and frame rate is necessary.

B. Requirements and restrictions on positioning sensors

Since global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) necessitate a permanent connection between multiple satellites and the UAV (see e.g. [8]), they are not an option during inspections inside bridges. Similarly, barometers, the use of which is established for in-flight altitude control on UAVs, are of only limited use in our setting as they rely on pressure difference measurements. Due to inevitable air pressure fluctuations near surfaces and in confined spaces, barometers are subject to high uncertainties [9], however.

While two of the established techniques used for UAV navigation, satellite-based navigation and barometer-based altitude measurements are not available, navigation based on inertial measurement units (IMU), which is also established for UAVs, is suitable in our situation. Because navigation

based on only IMUs is not sufficiently precise for our purposes, we combine IMUs with additional sensors, specifically with a laser-based range finder and a camera-based flow sensor, as detailed in the subsequent section.

In summary, an UAV ideal for our purposes must be as small as possible for use in confined and obstructed spaces. Small rotor size is desirable to reduce the ground effect and rotor-induced turbulences in general, while a lower bound on rotor size results because a sufficient thrust is required to carry a camera for crack detection. Finally, the setup must allow integration of additional sensors and sensor fusion with IMUs.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we introduce the UAV and communication setup that meet the requirements described in Sec. II, we briefly describe the ML model used for crack detection, and we describe the integration of the ML model into the UAV setup.

A. UAV Setup

We propose to use the bitcraze Crazyflie 2.1 quadcopter, which is shown in Fig. 2. UAVs of this type have successfully been used in several industrial applications such as gas detection [10], rescuing [11], and mapping for the assessment of radio signal quality [12]. The UAV has a rotor-to-rotor diameter of 130mm with a base takeoff weight of 27g. We use the smallest bitcraze propellers with a diameter of 45mm to reduce the ground effect. The payload amounts to 15g with this rotor type. The UAV is equipped with an STM32F405 microcontroller running bitcraze open-source flight software, as well as an industry-grade BMI088¹ IMU and a BMP388² pressure sensor³.

While IMU signals are suitable for basic flight stabilization tasks with characteristic time scales of 10-100ms, they are not sufficiently precise for navigation over longer periods of time (see e.g. [13]). Because GNSS signals, which are commonly combined with IMU and barometer signals in outdoor flights, are not available for the indoor flights to be carried out here, alternative signals are required to achieve

¹<https://www.bosch-sensortec.com/products/motion-sensors/>

²<https://www.bosch-sensortec.com/products/environmental-sensors/>

³<https://www.bitcraze.io/products/crazyflie-2-1/>

TABLE I
FEATURES OF THE SENSORS USED IN THE UAV SETUP

Type	Name	Accuracy	Sampling Rate
IMU	BMI088	$9 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{m/s}^2$	500Hz
Baro	BMP388	0.08hPa	100Hz
Range	VL531L1x	20mm	100Hz
Flow	PMW3901	-	100Hz

the desired precision over the entire flight time of the UAV. We use an optical flow sensor for this purpose. Optical flow sensors are known to be particularly good complements to IMUs [14] and they have successfully been used for navigation in GNSS-denied environments (see e.g. [15], [16]). Specifically, we use a bitcraze flow deck, which is equipped with a PMW3901 optical flow sensor⁴. At an additional mass of only 1.6g, the flow deck also provides a VL531L1x⁵ laser sensor for altitude measurements. The laser sensor complements the barometer. It is particularly advantageous for altitude measurements near surfaces, since it is less sensitive to the inevitable air pressure disturbances caused by the rotors. All signals are fused using an extended Kalman filter (see e.g. [17, Chapter 6]), where a linear Kalman filter does not suffice, since the UAV and measurement models are nonlinear⁶. The sensors and their most important features are summarized in Tab. I.

The camera used in this work is a Himax HM01B0 mounted on the bitcraze AI-Deck 1.1. The camera provides a monochrome image with a resolution of 320×320 pixels at 30 frames per second with an field of view (FOV) of 87° ⁷. The AI-Deck is equipped with an 8-core RISC-V MCU, flash memory, and an ESP32. The ESP32 is particularly useful as it enables communication with the deck through standard WiFi senders and receivers⁸. The AI-Deck weighs 4.4g. The UAV setup weight adds up to 33g, which is well below the maximum takeoff weight of 42g.

B. ML-based Crack Detection

We use an ML model trained for crack segmentation to enable autonomous crack detection. This model operates at the pixel level to identify cracks and their shapes (also called masks) within images (see Fig. 5a). It is based on a Feature Pyramid Network architecture and has been trained on a closed source dataset comprising over 5,500 original images of concrete damage with dimensions of 512×512 pixels. The dataset includes variations such as different lighting conditions [18]. To enhance the robustness of the ML model, additional data augmentation techniques, such as brightness change and blurring, were applied to the dataset to replicate extreme lighting conditions, such as

⁴<https://shop.pimoroni.com/products/pmw3901-optical-flow-sensor-breakout?variant=27869870358611>

⁵<https://www.st.com/en/imaging-and-photonics-solutions/vl531l1x.html>

⁶<https://www.bitcraze.io/documentation/repository/crazyflie-firmware/>

⁷<https://cdn.sparkfun.com/assets/b/3/e/8/e/HM01B0-MNA-Datasheet.pdf>

⁸<https://www.bitcraze.io/products/ai-deck/>

Fig. 3. Coupling of the UAV and the ML model. Solid lines indicate wired connections. Dashed lines indicate wireless connections.

those found inside bridges. The model was evaluated using the Intersection over Union (IoU) metric. The IoU metric, a common measure for object segmentation, calculates the ratio of the intersection to the union of the ground truth masks and ML prediction masks. The model achieved an IoU of 52.39%. It has been previously integrated and tested with various hardware platforms, including Microsoft’s HoloLens 2 for bridge inspections and the mobile robot Spot by Boston Dynamics for building defect inspections, as documented by the author’s previous studies [18], [19]. Further information on the dataset, the ML training, and comprehensive model results can be found in [18].

C. Integration of UAV flight control and crack detection

The ML-based crack detection is carried out on a ground station. The ground station is implemented on a standard PC, which also controls the trajectory flight of the UAV (see Fig. 3). Flight control commands are transmitted via a standard sender, specifically a bitcraze Crazyradio PA USB radio dongle, which operates on a 2.4GHz ISM band. All flight paths are implemented as point-by-point flights along pre-defined coordinates. Images are transferred from the camera and the AI-deck to the base station with the bitcraze WiFi image stream framework⁹, which runs on the AI-deck and which uses a WiFi channel provided by the ESP32 microcontroller. We note that it is crucial to use two separate channels for flight control commands on the one hand and image transmission on the other hand to achieve both a robust flight and a reliable transmission of images with the required frame rates.

To execute both flight control and crack detection simultaneously and in real-time, we use multi-threading with communication between both threads on the ground station. The first thread transmits the control commands and temporarily logs the UAV position estimates at a sampling frequency of 100Hz. The second thread retrieves the camera images from the AI-Deck 1.1 and processes them with the ML model. The images are upscaled from the camera’s native resolution of 320×320 pixels to the network resolution of 512×512 pixels. Upon the detection of a crack by the machine learning model in an image, the UAV logged position estimate from

⁹<https://www.bitcraze.io/documentation/repository/>

the first thread is permanently saved in the second thread. The setup can either signal in real-time that a crack has been detected, or record detected cracks for further analysis after the flight.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

We describe the general lab setup and show the combination of hardware and algorithms which is suitable for the task at hand. We first show that the low-resolution camera and the ML-based detection, are suitable with static images (i.e. not flying). Subsequently, we show that the setup is capable of detecting cracks in real-time during UAV flight.

A. Experimental Setup

All experiments are conducted in an indoor flight lab. Note that indoor flights mimic the conditions inside bridge structures described in Sec. II well.

We mount two images that show several different cracks under varying lighting conditions on a wall (see Fig. 4). The images are mounted with a diagonal offset to one another to model recurring flight trajectory types. Specifically, three trajectories are used in the experiments, a horizontal, a vertical and a diagonal flight (see Fig. 4). A distance of 40cm between the UAV and the wall and a velocity of 0.2m/s are maintained for all flights. We refer to each trajectory by the color it is shown with in Fig. 4. A fourth trajectory combines all three trajectories shown in the figure.

The light blue trajectory is flown to investigate the performance of the crack position estimation parallel to the ground. After reaching the initial height of 1.2m, the UAV follows a horizontal trajectory with a length of 2.4m crossing only the lower crack. The red trajectory starts at a height of 1m and is used to assess the performance of the crack position estimation when changing altitude. From the starting position, the UAV ascends 1.4m, reaching a total height of 2.4m, crossing only the upper crack. The green diagonal trajectory is 3.4m long. It starts at a height of 2.2m and crosses both the upper and lower crack. The fourth trajectory combines all three trajectories shown in Fig. 4 in the order blue, red, green. This fourth trajectory permits assessing both the performance over a longer period of time and the effect

Fig. 4. Location of crack images and trajectories for flight experiments.

Fig. 5. Comparison of detection results. a) High resolution image of the upper crack in Fig. 4 b) High resolution detection result of the crack. c) True positive result with good coverage with UAV-mounted camera. d) False negative result of the same crack structure due to increased distance to wall.

of changes in flight direction required when switching from one of the linear trajectories to the next.

Reference data for the UAV position is measured and recorded with a motion capture system. Specifically, 10 Vicon Vantage V5 infrared cameras and the software Tracker 3 were installed. This system can track objects equipped with an asymmetric pattern of reflective markers with a root mean squared error of less than 0.2mm¹⁰. The motion capture system sampling frequency is set to 100Hz, i.e., the same logging frequency as the proposed UAV setup. Whenever the UAV detects a crack, the current position of the UAV measured by the motion capture system is saved in parallel to the estimated position of the UAV as described in Sec. III-C. Before evaluation, we synchronize the motion capture system and UAV data to remove the phase shift between the two sets of data. We stress that this position reference data is only used to compare the detected crack locations to their actual location, where we consider location measured with the motion captures system to be the ground truth. The reference data generated with the motion capture system is not used by our UAV-based crack detection setup.

B. Experimental Results – Suitability of the Camera Signal

We first evaluate the performance of the crack detection on a single, still image captured by the UAV-mounted camera. This evaluation essentially corroborates that the ML model can be applied to the black-and-white images with 320 × 320 pixels even though the model has been trained for images with 512 × 512 color pixels. The ML model was not re-trained on images with smaller sizes as very fine crack information could be lost during resizing the training data.

Fig. 5 shows representative results of the detection with a single image. When the target distance to the wall is maintained, the ML model can detect the whole crack structure, even for fine cracks (see Fig. 5c). This shows that the network is suitable for black-and-white detection, as well as the upscaling not interfering with the detection. The image

¹⁰<https://www.vicon.com/>

Fig. 6. Measured UAV trajectories by motion capture system. Magenta markers indicate true UAV position when detecting a crack. Dark blue markers indicate the estimated UAV position when detecting a crack.

also remains stable, without blurring due to motion, which makes detection during movement possible. When the UAV is too far from the wall, the fine crack structures become difficult for the network to detect (see Fig. 5d). This shows the limitation of the low resolution camera in combination with fine cracks. To increase the detection rate, the results could be accumulated over multiple frames.

C. Results – In-flight Detection and Crack Localization

Fig. 6 illustrates the performance of the in-flight crack detection. The ML model now evaluates the camera frames that are continuously sent from the UAV to the PC while the UAV flies along the paths from Fig. 4. Whenever the ML model detects a crack in the current frame, the current position of the UAV is stored. The resulting positions are marked with blue circles in Fig. 6. At the same time, the position measured with the motion capture system for reference is marked with a magenta circle. The offset between a set of blue circles and its corresponding set of magenta circles is a first indication of how precisely our crack detection setup can locate cracks.

The sets of circles in Fig. 6 form lines with few interruptions. This indicates cracks are continuously detected once a crack moves into the field of vision of the camera and until it moves out again. We checked the frames by visual inspection and found false negatives to be rare. False positives were not encountered during any flight.

The average evaluation time of an image across all experiments is 255ms with a standard deviation of 10ms. This result yields 3.9 evaluated images per second or, considering the velocity of 0.2m/s, an evaluated image every 5.1cm. Taking into account the FOV of the camera and the constant distance between UAV and wall, the camera can capture a quadratic segment of the wall with a side length of 76cm making the evaluation speed sufficient to ensure no loss of information.

Fig. 6 collects the results for each of the blue, red and green trajectories from Fig. 4. Colored lines in Fig. 6 visualize the actual trajectories flown by the UAV as measured by the motion capture system.

It is evident from the blue and green trajectories (Figs. 6 (a) and (c), respectively) first that the UAV never achieves

the full intended distances in y -direction. For the blue trajectory, the UAV is supposed to fly a distance of 2.4m, but finishes its flight already at 2m. For the flight along the green trajectory, a maximal deviation of 0.5m between estimated and true position results at the end of the flight. Closer inspection of the data reveals that the offset between estimated and true position increases by 17cm for every meter moved, when no changes in direction occur. The offset can be explained by the characteristic of the sensors used for position estimation. Position estimation along the y -axis is based on IMU and optical flow measurements. Both sensors measure only relative changes in position, which are summed or integrated over time to obtain information about flown distances. Measurement errors are also integrated and cannot be corrected by the Kalman Filter due to the lack of absolute position measurements, such as those available from GNSS positioning in unobstructed environments. As a result, the deviation between estimated and true UAV position when detecting a crack increases as the travelled distance increases. Maximum and average offsets are summarized in Tab. II. These offsets seem to be large at first sight, but we claim they still provide a proper overview of the size and distribution of cracks. This is also evident when comparing the detected crack locations to the actual location of cracks in Fig. 6.

It remains to analyse the the precision of the crack estimation along the z -axis (red trajectory, Fig. 6 (b)). In this case, offsets are very small with no systematic accumulation over time. This behavior differs from that for the position estimation along the y -axis as the integrated IMU measurements are now corrected with altitude information by

TABLE II
DEVIATIONS BETWEEN ESTIMATED AND TRUE UAV POSITION WHEN DETECTING A CRACK

Trajectory	Light Blue	Red	Green	Combined
Max y	37.4cm	8.7cm	56.6cm	27.7cm
Average y	23.6cm	6.5cm	27.4cm	10.0cm
Max z	0.6cm	11.2cm	1.4cm	3.1cm
Average z	0.3cm	3.1cm	0.9cm	1.6cm

Fig. 7. Measured UAV trajectory for investigation of long-time performance. Magenta markers indicate true UAV position when detecting a crack. Dark blue markers indicate estimated UAV position when detecting a crack.

the pressure and laser sensor. In contrast to the acceleration information provided by the IMU, the pressure and laser sensors do not need to be integrated. Consequently, they are not as prone to error accumulation due to integration. The average deviation between estimated and true UAV position when detecting a crack along the z -axis of only 3.1cm underlines the performance of the proposed setup. This result also indicates that the precision of the location measurements in x - and y -directions is likely to improve dramatically if an additional absolute distance information, e.g. from known dimensions of an inspected wall, is available.

Finally, we evaluate the performance of our system over a longer time span by analysing the fourth flight trajectory. We briefly recall this trajectory combines the three previous trajectories in one single flight. Apart from a longer flight time, this implies multiple changes of directions are involved. The UAV starts by flying horizontally first before following the other trajectories counter-clockwise. For the first two flight segments, this experiment yields comparable results to the previous ones (see Fig. 7). However, as soon as the flight direction changes for the second time, the horizontal offsets begin to decrease. The integration of measurement errors in one direction of movement obviously compensates previous integration errors of movements in the opposite direction. Consequently, both the maximum deviation and the average deviation between estimated and true UAV position along the y -axis when detecting a crack are lower for long flights than for isolated trajectories, assuming there are changes in the direction of flight. This implies, somewhat counter-intuitively, that frequent changes in direction, which would actually be natural since supporting structures are not likely to provide long free path lengths, help achieving a higher localization precision.

V. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

We addressed the challenge of the autonomous inspection of the inside of bridge structures. We demonstrated nano UAV are capable of carrying the equipment required for machine learning assisted crack detection and position estimation in the absence of satellite-based positioning signals.

Future work will focus on strategies of how to sys-

tematically explore narrow indoor environments and path planning algorithms if cracks are detected. This will require extensions of the machine learning model and sensor fusion with position clues from known layouts of the inspected cavities.

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